

A Study on Effectiveness of Training with Special References for TVS Training and Service Pvt Ltd Chennai

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ABSTRACT

The project is a research study aimed to find out the effectiveness of training in the work place and its cause with special reference for TVS Training and service PVT LTD Chennai. Training and development to collect the employee's satisfaction and their of the employees to meet the customer satisfaction Training effectiveness is fundamentally an evaluation that inspects the level to which training enhanced the employee's skill, knowledge, and behavior inside the association The perception of training effectiveness is a series of Many factors on the situation of the pre-training stage, training stage, post-training stage and personal factors. If potential, the branches are obtained in such a Manner that it tested with data. For several types of information, such type of data is not available current; others May perhaps desire to reorganize in available data. The variance in the training process is related to the diversity of the specification and the trainees that legally responsible, the degree of intricacy of the intervening opportunity and obstacles and also with the evaluation of the financial system.

KEYWORDS: Effectiveness, Training Skills

A. INTRODUCTION

Training is a process of learning and understanding the sequence of programmed activities it is application of knowledge it gives people an awareness of the rules and procedure to guide their behaviors. It attempts to better their performance on the current job or prepare for an predetermined job. Effectiveness of Training them can be one of the most important contributions a business can make. The right training can ensure that your business has the right expertise to tackle the future. It can also help entice and keep good quality staff, as well as increasing the job satisfaction of those presently with you - increasing the chances that they will satisfy your customers. Thus Training is the ad of increasing the knowledge and skills of employee. It is an intrinsic truth that the human resources available in an organization have to be managed more efficiently than the material resources comprising of machines and money. Expressive putting "Training is a structured growth of the knowledge, skills and attitudes required by employees to perform sufficient on a given task or job.

B. Research Methodology

Research ways of doing things is a way to in and organized way solve the research problem it refers not to the research methods but also the logic behind the methods use in the research study why only particular methods used why certain methods and ways of doing things are not used and so on. Why a research study has been defined, what data has

been collected, what method has been adopted and a host of similar questions are usually answered when it is comes to research ways of doing things.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Research design is an arrangement of condition for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purposes with the economy in procedure .A research. The research should specific the approach with respect to the proposed study. classified two types Namely

- Descriptive research
- Conclusive research

This study is more explanatory in nature, which defines as a research design to plan educated guess potential (related to) possible problems and opportunities present in the decent situation. This study helps to exact the almost defined problem and gives a different way of seeing things (related to) the different (things that changes). More than that, this study establishes (things that are the most important), gain (way of seeing things), identifies different solutions and gather information. In this study of employee's performance judgment. The association of different (things that change) is also decide to some extent here.

- Type of Research
- Title of research

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- Area of research
- Period of research
- Sampling techniques
- Data collection methods
- Tools used for analysis
- Scope of study
- Limitations on the study

Type of research:

The research is descriptive in nature. It includes surveys and fact finding investigation of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is description of the state of affair as it exists at present.

Title of the research

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCES FOR TVS TRAINING AND SERVICE PVT LTD CHENNAI

Area of research

The study is conducted in Chennai

Period of research

The study period is 5 months

Sampling techniques:

Sample size for the study was selected on the basis of simple random sampling method, 100 employees are randomly selected as sample.

Data collection methods:

Data are collected from both primary & secondary sources. Primary data are collected through structured questionnaire and secondary data are collected from official website of the company, journals, articles, textbooks, etc...

Tools used for analysis:

The following analytical tools are used for data analysis

- Percentage
- Average
- Chi Square
- In view of the limited time available for the study, only the Effectiveness of Training process could be studied.
- The sample size is too small to reflect the opinion of the whole organization.

Scope of the study:

- The establishment of any organization depends on the employees. For organizational productivity Effectiveness of Training assumes great significance.
- The study is conducted to know the level of accomplishment and ability given to the employees in the organization.

Limitations on the study:

- In view of the limited time available for the study, only the Effectiveness of Training process could be studied.
- The sample size is too small to absorb the opinion of the whole organization.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE:

To conduct and study a Training and development need Analysis with special reference to TVS Training and service pvt ltd Chennai.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES:

- To understand the employees understanding about training needs. To analyze the existing training detail and its benefit.
- To develop an effective and viable training system according to the requirement.
- To study the effectiveness of training in overall growth of skills of workforce.

Questionnaire Design:

Questionnaire used for data collection is designed based on the fulfillment of the objectives of the study. The Questionnaire contains demographic and socioeconomic profile of the respondents, various attributes & factors related to Motivation was used in the Questionnaire, some close ended & dichotomous questions were used. The title of the study deal as "A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL TOWARDS RK HOSPITAL REFERENCE TO THANJA

C. Chi Square

Hypothesis:

Null hypothesis:

There is no relationship between age and the gender respondent's perception towards to enhance Effectiveness of training

Calculated value of $\chi^2 = 6.96$

Degree of freedom = $(C - 1) \times (r - 1) = (4 - 1) \times (2 - 1) = 3$

The table value of χ^2 for 4 degree of freedom at 5 per cent level of significance is 3.83

Conclusion:

Calculated value of chi square is more than the table value, so the null hypothesis is rejected..

D. ANOVA

Hypothesis:

Null hypothesis:

There is no significant ANOVA between education qualification and effectiveness of training

Conclusion:

calculated F value is 11.72 and F critical value 3.88 so calculated value is more than the table value so Null is rejected .

E. CORRELATION:

Calculation value is 0.585 and so I correlation between Rate statement and effectiveness of training

Findings

- 68% of respondents belongs to the male class.
- 48% of the respondents are in the age of 18 to 20 yrs.
- 68% of the respondents are Diploma holders
- 71% of the respondents are married
- 55% of the respondents are having 1 to 2 month of experience.
- 48% of the respondents the time duration for the training periods is sufficient.
- 63% of the respondents satisfied of the training
- 39% percentage of the respondents the training is provide by TVS for on the job

- 58% of the respondents the are conducted category for Rigorour
- 35% of the respondents are disagree the for the company conducts training frequently
- 39% respondents are neutral
- the is planed exercise in your organization
- 42% respondents are agree the organization provide as much as ongoing training as you need to perform your task.
- 51% percentage of the respondents agree the instructor response to doubles.
- 48% of the respondents the training is well planned strongly agree
- 42% of the respondents are strongly agree suffering duration
- 38% of the respondents strongly agree I feel management takes most about employee training program is effectiveness of training
- 33% of the respondents are imporment of knowledge of the training is strongly agree
- 43% of the respondents are normal the working environment.
- 42% of the respondents are agree improve performance of training
- 56% of the respondents are satisfied the effectiveness of training programs in good
- 51% of the respondents are after training programs yes feed nature of the job
- 73% of the respondent are yes training is given according to the employee need
- 96% respondents are yes indurations training is of suffient duration

Suggestions

- Provide adequate training program to each and every person arranged accordingly. The result of the training program also should be analyses and training should be arranged periodically.
- Company has to introduce effective training in every department of the firm so as it help to learn more knowledge in the subject
- Provide employees motivation programs and other training programs for the development towards profit

making.

- On the job training and off the job training is equally important. Provide both the training continuously to the employees.
- Skill based training (Product / Process Training) should be provided. Besides questionnaires other methods of post training evaluation should also be used like interviews , self-diaries ,
- Observations, and supplement test
- Post training has to be continuous and should be taken¹ from line manager / superior and from peers to find out the effectiveness and valuation of training

Conclusion:

In conclusion, effectiveness of training is extremely important to the growth of the company. They not only improve the employee's potential and knowledge but also buildup the relationship that exists between the labor force and the members of management within the company. Training begins when it is direct that there is a necessary. The need helps to determine in how the training will be designed and implemented. Employee training is a process that requires planning. This planning includes who is in requisite of training, what types of training are best suited for those in want, the arrangement, which includes the training activities and equipment, the actual training, as well as the training budget and the follow up assessment are all included in the training. Employee training is actually an answer to a company or an employee want. His success of the training is measured over time and is based upon whether or not the employee's knowledge or skills increased as a result of the training.

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